

INFLUENCE OF SURFACE ROUGHNESS ON THE MODE II FATIGUE RESISTANCE OF THE BONDED COMPOSITE-TO-STEEL INTERFACE

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ABSTRACT

The use of bonded joints have been increasing in FRP strengthened steel structures. The bond quality highly relies on the surface roughness of the steel elements. This paper investigates the influence of steel surface roughness on the mode II fatigue resistance of the bonded composite-to-steel joints. Fatigue 4-point end notch flexure (4ENF) tests are conducted, with the steel adherend prepared with low, medium and high roughness. Results show that under fatigue loads, no fiber bridging is found for all the roughness levels. Increase of roughness can improve the fatigue resistance significantly while the slope of Paris curve remain similar.

KEYWORDS

Bonded joints; 4ENF test; DIC; Paris curves; Surface roughness

INTRODUCTION

The bonded joint has been widely utilised in FRP strengthened steel structures due to its enhanced stress transfer mechanisms and design flexibility (Borrie et al., 2021). While providing sufficient strengthening effect, the bonded composite/steel joints are still suffering debonding failure at the interface under extreme loading conditions, e.g. fatigue loading (Wahab et al., 2012). The surface preparation of the adherends plays an important role for avoiding such failure modes. An appropriate preparation should provide sufficient surface roughness of the steel plate.

Different surface preparation techniques have been used in common practice for the bonded steel plate such as blasting, etching, grinding, laser structing etc., among which the grit blasting proved to be the most convenient and effective one (Mandolino et al., 2013; Rudawska, 2014; Saborowski et al., 2019). Most of the results showed that the static bond strength and/or fracture toughness of the joint increases with the roughness, which is mainly due to the increased effective bond area and enhanced mechanical interlocking between the adherends, while excessive roughness may lead to decrease of the static performance (Hwang et al., 2018; van Dam et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2012). In addition, inducing a rougher crack propagation path has shown to increase the fracture toughness of a bonded joint (Arouche et al., 2021).

Besides the static behaviour, the influence of surface roughness on the fatigue performance of bonded joints have also been studied. S. Azari et al. (Azari et al., 2010) investigated the effect of roughness on the adhesive steel joints under cyclic loading by DCB and ADCB tests. They found that the fatigue threshold strain energy release rate G_{th} increased with the roughness, reached a plateau, then decreased for very rough surfaces. The increase of G_{th} is mainly due to increased bonding area, crack growth retardation due to crack path deflection around asperities, while the decrease was attributed to the increase in stress concentration at the tip of the roughness asperities, and also to void formation at the interface. Bernardo Carrera (Carrera, 2022) investigated the total fatigue life, stiffness degradation and residual static strength of CFRP-to-steel joints with different surface conditions. It shows that the fatigue life is not affected by the surface characteristic. Specimens with higher roughness have a slower of stiffness degradation under low to moderate fatigue loads compared to specimens with smooth

surfaces. Katsuki Shikimoto et al. (Shikimoto et al., 2020) investigated the effect of laser patterning pre-processing on fatigue strength of adhesive bonded joints using thin steel plate. The fatigue tests showed that the laser patterning can significantly improve the fatigue strength of the bond.

It can be seen that although the static performance has been maturely studied, the influence of surface roughness on the fatigue behaviour of bonded joints has not been thoroughly investigated. Furthermore, existing research related to the fatigue behaviour mainly focused on the total fatigue life of the joints. The present work investigates the influence of surface roughness on the fatigue crack growth properties of the bonded composite-to-steel joints. Fatigue 4-point end-notched flexure (4ENF) tests are conducted for specimens with different surface roughness. The surface roughness is finally correlated with the fatigue resistance, namely the Paris curve parameters.

SPECIMENS

In this study, a total of 9 bonded joint specimens, 3 specimens for 3 different roughness series, were used for the fatigue 4ENF tests as shown in Table 1. In the specimen notation, 'RL/RM/RH' denotes low, medium, and high roughness levels, respectively. 'F' represents fatigue tests, and the number of specimens within each series is indicated at the end. For each series, desired steel surface roughness is achieved by grit blasting. Surface roughness of the steel plates were measured by a 3D optical profilometer (Keyence VR6000) with 40× magnification before applying the composite laminates. Two 20×20 mm areas on the steel plates of each roughness series were selected and scanned. Representative optical images and 3D profiles for each roughness are shown in Figure 1. It can be seen that, compared to the relatively smooth surface of low roughness series, more sharp peaks and valleys are found in the medium and high roughness series. The root mean square height, S_q , is chosen as the parameter to evaluate the roughness and listed in Table 1 for each series.

Table 1: Specimens and roughness

Specimens	Total thickness (mm)	Roughness S_q (μm)
RL-F-1/2/3	17.64±0.27	4.56±0.75
RM-F-1/2/3	17.47±0.37	14.14±1.24
RH-F-1/2/3	15.38±0.25	21.99±0.62

Figure 1 Optical images and 3D profiles of steel surface with different roughness

The composite laminates are manufactured by hand lay-up of the glass fiber plies on the steel treated surface. Before applying the laminates, surfaces of steel plates are chemically degreased to ensure good bonding quality. The composite ply is formed by woven interleaved with chopped strand mat (CSM) and a vinyl ester matrix system with fibre volume fraction of approximately 30%. Mild steel S355 is

employed for the steel plate. Geometry and dimensions of the specimens used in this study are shown in Figure 2. For the bi-material configuration, the thicknesses of steel and composites are designed to meet the criterion described in Eq. 1, such that the two arms have the same longitudinal strain at the faying surfaces to obtain a pure mode II loading condition (Arouche et al., 2022):

$$E_1 h_1^2 = E_2 h_2^2 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where E_1 and E_2 are the elastic modulus in the longitudinal direction for the upper and lower arms, respectively. However, due to variation of applied pressure during hand lamination and curing conditions afterwards, the thickness of the specimens vary among different roughness series. The measured average total thickness of the specimens are listed in Table 1. A non-adhesive insert of $32 \mu\text{m}$ thickness is inserted at one end of the specimens to induce a pre-crack between steel and composite arms. After being produced, the plates are cut into specimens with the designed width using water jet. The white paint followed by a black speckle pattern is applied on one side of the specimens for crack monitoring by digital image correlation (DIC).

Figure 2: Geometry and dimensions of the specimen (in millimetres)

TEST METHOD

The 4-point bending test set-up is shown in Figure 3. A universal testing machine coupled with a load cell of 15 kN is used to conduct the tests. The specimens are loaded by two loading cylinders attached to the loading beam, which is connected to the actuator by a shaft such that equal loading forces can be achieved in the two loading points. The tests are conducted by displacement control with the frequency of 4Hz. The starting force level is chosen to be around 60% of the critical load. A digital camera assisted by a LED light is positioned perpendicularly to the specimen during the tests, serving as the 2D DIC system for crack length monitoring. With the camera connected to the controlling system, photos are taken at the minimum and maximum forces every 500 cycles or every 1% stiffness degradation. Shear strains are extracted at the interface afterwards during the DIC analysis and are quantified by the strain thresholds to determine the crack length. The explanation of crack monitoring technique can be found in Ref. (Feng et al., 2023).

Figure 3: Test set-up and instrumentation

FRACTURE DATA ANALYSIS

The crack growth driving force, i.e. the strain energy release rates (SERR), are calculated by the extended global method (EGM), proposed by Shahverdi et al. (Shahverdi et al., 2014) based on the global method (Williams, 1988).

The global method is developed based on the beam theory where the SERR is calculated by the bending moments and loads in a cracked laminate. EGM extended the application of the global method to consider the asymmetric case where the crack propagates between two different orthotropic layers. According to EGM, mode II SERR at the crack tip of 4ENF specimens can be calculated as:

$$G_{II,4ENF} = \frac{P^2 L_a^2}{8BE_1 I_1} \left(\frac{1}{1+\psi} - \xi \right) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where ψ and ξ are the bending stiffness ratios of arms for the specimens, which can be calculated by:

$$\psi = \frac{E_2 I_2}{E_1 I_1} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$\xi = \frac{E_1 I_1}{(EI)_{eq}} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

In Eq. 2, 3 and 4, E_1 and E_2 are the longitudinal modulus of the upper and lower arms. I_1 and I_2 are the moment of inertia of the upper lower arms, respectively. $(EI)_{eq}$ is the equivalent bending stiffness of the specimen.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Failure modes

After the tests, the specimens are opened along the fracture interface for further inspection. The optical images and height profiles of each roughness series are shown in Figure 4. It is found that the predominate failure mode for all roughness series is adhesion failure at the composite-to-steel interface. The fracture surface of low and medium roughness specimens is smooth with only a small portion of resin remaining on the steel surface. The fracture surface of higher roughness specimen is rougher with one piece of tearing fibre remaining on the steel surface, but still no significant fiber bridging is observed. This means that regardless the surface roughness, the strain energy required to propagate the crack at the composite-to-steel interface is less than that within composite layers under cyclic loads.

b) Medium roughness series

c) High roughness series

Figure 4: Fracture surface of specimens

Crack growth and SERR evolution

The SERR variations of each specimen during the cyclic tests are calculated by the EGM and summarized in Figure 5. The crack length, a , determined by analysing the shear strains at the interface is also shown in the same figure for comparison. Results of RL-F-3 is missing due to malfunction of the DIC system during the test. It can be seen from the figure that results of each specimen within each roughness series are reproducible. Under displacement control, the SERR values drop rapidly at the initial stage and stabilize gradually as the test continues. This is due to the fact that the force decreases gradually under displacement control as the crack propagates. Driven by the SERR at the crack tips, the crack grows fast at the initial stage, but gradually slows down as the SERR decreases. The tests were stopped until that no further crack growth can be detected by the DIC system. Except for the low roughness specimens where the crack growth stabilises at 165 mm, crack growth for other two roughness series both stabilises at around 220 mm, corresponding to the location of the right loading cylinders.

a) low roughness series

b) medium roughness series

c) high roughness series

Figure 5: Fatigue crack growth curves and SERR development

Fatigue resistance curves

In order to obtain the fatigue resistance curves, namely the Paris curves, the crack growth rate, da/dN , is calculated by the secant method as shown in Eq. 5.

$$da / dN_{\bar{a}} = (a_{i+1} - a_i) / (N_{i+1} - N_i) \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where i represents the i th data point. The average crack length in each crack increment, $\bar{a} = (a_{i+1} + a_i)$ is used to calculate the corresponding SERR. The crack growth rates are plotted against ΔG_{II} in Figure 6 and are fitted by a power function as described in Eq. 6 such that the fatigue resistance curves can be obtained:

$$da / dN = C(\Delta G_{II})^m \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where C and m are fitted parameters which determines the intercept and slope of the Paris curves. They are determined by the least squares method and listed in Table 2 for each roughness series. It can be seen from Figure 6 that Paris curves from different roughness series are generally parallel to each other, namely showing similar slopes (m values in the same magnitude). However, the position of the curves changes a lot among different roughness, with the C parameter decreasing from over 1 to the magnitude of 10^{-2} as the roughness increases. This means that the fatigue resistance of high roughness series can be over 100 times higher than the low roughness series at the SERR range of 1N/mm. However, it should be noted that the fatigue resistance of RM series can be higher than the RH series at relatively low (e.g. below 0.1N/mm) SERR ranges due to the higher curve slope (m value) of the RM series.

Figure 6: Paris curves of different roughness

Table 2: Paris curve parameters of different roughness series

Specimens	C	m	C'
RL-F	1.70	3.30	1.99
RM-F	0.04	3.97	0.051
RH-F	0.01	3.07	0.0078
Average	-	3.45	-

The m values are plotted against the roughness parameter S_q in Figure 7 a). Although the m value shows an increasing then decreasing trend as the roughness increases, the variation is within an acceptable scattering range of 3-4, which is insignificant compared with the over-magnitudes variation of C parameter. Meanwhile, considering the fact that there may be no physical reason for the m parameter to be higher in the medium roughness level than the other roughness levels, it is reasonable to state that the m parameter doesn't change with the roughness levels.

Another reason to keep the m parameter fixed is to re-fit all the Paris' curves with a constant slope. In such case, the C parameter can truly reflect the fatigue resistance for different roughness levels, instead of only representing the crack growth rate at $\Delta G_{II}=1\text{N/mm}$. The average value of m , 3.45, is taken as the fixed slope. The new fitted Paris curves are plotted as dash lines in Figure 6. The newly obtained C parameters, C' , are listed in Table 2 and are plotted against the roughness parameter S_q in Figure 7 b). Compared with the initial C parameters, the new C' parameters change slightly due to the fixed m values. It can be seen from Figure 7 b) that the C' parameter decreases as the roughness increases. Generally speaking, the C' parameter becomes one order of magnitude lower when the roughness increases from the low level to the medium level, and also from the medium level to the high level. Considering the variation trend of C parameter, a power function, Eq. 7, is used to depict the relationship between C and roughness parameters:

$$C = k(S_q)^l \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where k and l are the fitted parameters, determined by the least squares method with the fitted results shown in the figure.

It is proved that the fatigue resistance of the composite-to-steel bonded joints is sensitive to the surface roughness of the steel adherend. It can be sufficiently ensured as long as an appropriate surface preparation is applied on the steel plates before joining. It has been widely discussed in literature that the improvement of bonding performance as surface roughness increases is due to the increased effective bonding area. Furthermore, the highly textured surface of high roughness series as shown in Figure 1 makes it easier for the adhesive to deeply penetrate into the steel surface, enhancing the

mechanical interlocking between steel and composites. Considering the failure mode as adhesive failure at the interface for all roughness levels, the fatigue resistance is highly influenced by the roughness features on the steel surfaces, which is different from the literature (Azari et al., 2010) which states that the fatigue performance is insensitive to the surface roughness when the crack path moved farther away from the interface.

Figure 7: Variation of Paris curve parameters versus roughness

CONCLUSIONS

In the current study, the influence of surface roughness of the steel adherend on the mode II fatigue resistance of the bonded composite-to-steel interface was investigated using 4ENF tests. The steel surface roughness was measured before lamination of the composite and the failure modes were observed after tests. It is concluded that, under cyclic loading conditions, no fibre bridging is observed at the interface for all roughness series. The slope of Paris curve, m , varies slightly as the roughness changes. But the C parameter decreases drastically, generally becomes one order of magnitude lower when the roughness increases from low to medium and medium to high levels. The means that the fatigue resistance of the bonded joint can be sufficiently ensured as long as an appropriate surface preparation is applied. The enhancing effect of fatigue resistance with increased roughness is mainly due to the increased bonding areas. Other mechanisms such as the highly textured surface which enhances the mechanical interlocking between steel and composites may also take effect.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

CITATIONS

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